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Review Article

Formulation And Evaluation of Natural Anti-Aging Cream

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ABSTRACT

Skin aging is a complex process induced by constant exposure to UV radiation and damages the human skin. UV generates reactive oxygen species leading to collagen deficiency and eventually skin wrinkling. There is a growing demand for herbal products in the world market and they are invaluable gift of nature. Therefore, edible cream containing natural ingredients such as mung bean, olive oil, aloe vera etc., has been prepared. These natural ingredients not only give beneficiary effect to the skin but also does not show any side effect as of artificial cream produces side effect when applied to the skin. The cream was formulated using different concentrations G1, G2 and G3. G2 formulation was found with good consistency and stability of 7 days by performing accelerated stability testing at different temperature and humidity conditions. It can be concluded that herbal cream without side effects can be used as provision of a barrier to protect the skin and avoid aging of the skin.

INTRODUCTION

Skin aging is gradual deterioration of mature organism resulting from time dependent and reversible changes in the structure. Aging process is observed because of sequential skin aging and photo aging. Both have different features. Sequential skin aging is universal process characterised by physiological Alterations in skin functions. In the aging process keratinocytes aren't able to form a functional stratum corneum and rate of formation, from neutral lipids slows down. It is characterised by dry pale skin and wrinkles. And

photo aging is caused due to over exposure to sun. UV generates reactive oxygen species leading to collagen deficiency and skin wrinkling. It is characterised by dry and pale skin with deep furrows that is caused by disorganisation of dermal and epidermal components. Anti-aging cosmetics is a branch of cosmetics which deals with the removal of signs of aging. The anti-aging ingredients present in the anti-aging cosmetics helps to reduce the fine lines and increase the moisture level of the skin. And its main function is to reduce wrinkles and puffiness from the skin.

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The demand of herbal cosmetics is rapidly expanding, this expansion is due to availability of new ingredients, the financial rewards for developing successful products, consumer demand, and a better understanding of skin physiology. The ingredients used in the preparation should have varieties of properties like antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, antiseptic and antibacterial activity etc.

Literature review:

1. T. Mangilal, KSK Rao Patnaik, R Shyam Sunder and S Anuradha Bai 2017 Preparation and evaluation of polyherbal anti-aging cream by using different synthetic polymers. International journal of Herbal medicine.
2. Ashish Aswal, Mohini Kalra and Abhiram Rout 2015 Preparation and evaluation of polyherbal cosmetic cream. Der Pharmacia Lettre.
3. Sanjit kumar kar and Tushar kanti Bera 2017 Phytochemical constituents of aloe vera and their multifunctional properties: A comprehensive review. International journal of pharmaceutical sciences and research: project impact factor (2018):0.83, Cite Score.

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Aim And Objective:

Aim: Formulation And Evaluation Of Natural Anti-Aging Cream.

Objective of the study:

1. Formulation of the poly herbal anti-ageing cream using the extracts.
2. To prevent aging of skin
3. To reduce the rate of premature ageing
4. To nourish and beautify the skin.
5. Priliminary phytochemical investigation of different extract of the plants.

Plan Of Work:

The present proposed research work is planned as follows:

- 1) literature Review
- 2) selection of suitable constituents for preparation of natural anti aging cream.
- 3) collection of constituents from plant parts.
- 4) preparation of natural anti aging cream.
- 5) evaluation of natural anti aging cream.
- 6) result and discussion.
- 7) conclusion.

Formulation Table:

Ingredients	% W/W
Ginger decoction	To 100.0
Aloe Vera Gel	5.0
Mung bean	1.0
Olive oil	5.0
Natural butter	5.0
Acacia/ corn starch	2.0
Honey	5.0
Preservative	0.1
Colouring agent	—
pH adjuster	Q.S

Formulation And Evaluation of Natural Anti-Aging Cream:

PHASE I

Phase I ingredients are mixed using homogenizer (50 mm) and heated up to.

Phase II

Phase II ingredients are mixed and heated up to 60° C-70° C until uniform consistency is formed. Phase I and phase II are mixed together at the same temperature to form.

Phase III

Phase II ingredients are added to semisolid mixture at a temperature of 40° C Adjust the pH of the cream to 7.4-7.6 by using pH adjuster.

Evaluation Parameter:

Apperance:

The appearance of the cream was judge by its colour, pearl scence and roughness.

All of the cream:

The pH meter was calibrated using standard buffer solution about 0.5g of the cream was wrighed and dissolved in 50ml of distilled water and its pH was measured.

Viscosity:

Viscosity of the formulation was determined by Brookfield viscometer. The viscosity measurements were done using Brookfield DV-II + viscometer using LV-4 spindle. The developed formulation was poured into the adapter of the viscometer and the angular velocity increased gradually fom 0.5 to 20r/min.

Stability study:

The purpose of stability testing is to provide evidence on how the. Quality of drug substance or drug product varies with time under the influence of variety of environmental factors such temperature, humidity and light and enables to recommend storage condition and to predict the shelf life. Stability study for cream was performed at accelerated condition ic40°C+2°C/75%RH+5%RH.

RESULT:

To formulate and evaluate of anti-aging cream was performed with expected outcomes it has good lability pli viscosity and stability studios

Ief formulation 7.3

Colour light pink

Order aromatic

Fig. Antiaging Cream

CONCLUSION:

The usage of natural cosmetics has been increased to many folds in personal care system and there is a great demand for natural cosmetics. The use of bioactive ingredients in cosmetics influence biological functions of the skin and provide nutrients necessary for healthy skin. The anti-aging cream slow down the skin aging by regenerating and activating the cells and protect against ultraviolet rays, free radicals. As artificial cosmetics give many side effects it's better to use cream prepared by natural ingredients as does not show any side effect rather is beneficial to skin.

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